

THE CURRENT STATE OF STUDENTS' FORMATION OF THE SKILLS TO WORK IN INDEPENDENT EDUCATION IN THE CREDIT MODULE SYSTEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12089937>

Abstract: In the "Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", introduction of digital technologies and modern teaching methods into higher education processes, wide involvement of young people in scientific activities, fight against corruption, engineering and technical education specific tasks have been defined to increase the share of students studying in science, to introduce the credit-module system, to increase the share of practical training in specialized subjects aimed at improving practical skills in the curricula. This indicates that almost all higher education institutions in the country will start operating in the credit-module system in the coming years. The credit-module system is a process of educational organization and is an evaluation model based on a set of module technologies of education and a credit measure. Carrying it out as a whole is a complex and systematic process. This article reviews the current state of forming the skills and qualifications of students to work in independent education in the future credit-module system in the course of higher education.

Key words: Credit module system, individual activity, independent education, skills, audience, intensive study, concept, assessment rating.

Introduction:

Today's credit-module system of educational process organization is a model of educational process organization based on a combination of modular teaching technologies and credit or credit education units.

In the "Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", introduction of digital technologies and modern teaching methods into higher education processes, wide involvement of young people in scientific activities, fight against corruption, engineering and technical education or Specific tasks have been defined to increase the share of students studying in the fields of study, to introduce the credit-module system, to increase the share of practical training in specialized subjects aimed at increasing practical skills in the curricula. According to the "Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 8, 2019, 85 percent of the higher education institutions in the country will gradually transition to the credit-module system until 2030¹. This indicates that almost all higher education institutions in the country will start operating in the credit-module system in the coming years.

Literature review:

¹ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining Farmoni, 08.10.2019 yildagi PF-5847-son

In modern pedagogical literature, there are four types of independent activity in the educational process, each of which is distinguished by its own characteristics of planning and post-new goals, namely:

- setting goals and planning activities with the help of the teacher;
- only goal setting is done with the help of the teacher, work planning is done independently by the student;
- goal setting and planning are carried out independently by the student within the framework of the task set by the teacher;
- the work is carried out by the student on his own initiative: he determines the content, purpose, plan of the work himself without the help of the teacher and performs it independently.

A number of pedagogues conducted scientific research on the formation of students' knowledge and skills in the credit module system, including: N.E.Azimova, M.E.Akhmedova, O.V.Treskina, YE.V.Siganova, Z.Q.Ismoilova, X.A.Kadirova, SH.Kh Kenjayev, G.I. Makhmutova, Z.T. Saliyeva and others we will be able to see in the researches.

It is also covered in the research works of SH.Z.Taylanova, J.S.Toshmatova, Z.B.Jalilov, S.U.Mavlonova, R.Mamatkulova, K.N.Kudryavsev, T.N.Panayeva, I.A.Cherkashin regarding the organization of independent educational activities and the development of students' skills.

Method and materials:

The introduction of the credit-module system is an important factor in stimulating the effective work of the teacher and the student. The concept of module and credit - modules are developed as a system of educational elements combined with a sign of conformity to a specific object of professional activity. The second is considered as a certain amount of information with an independent logical structure and content, which allows working with this information in the course of the student's mental activity.

According to foreign experience, the educational process in the credit-module system consists of 2-4 modules per semester. The subjects included in the module are formed from easy to complex, from theoretical-methodical subjects to applied subjects and based on the principle of logical complementarity. In order for a student to become a specialist, it is necessary not only to acquire information, but also to be able to process it and put it into practice.

Module-based training programs are developed based on a special scheme and include:

- full disclosure of educational goals and tasks;
- requirements for the qualification that the student must acquire after starting and finishing the subject (course);
- a summary (syllabus) of each subject included in the module, i.e. topics of lectures, a plan of seminars and practical exercises, tasks intended for independent education assessment;
- a summary of teaching: methods and means of teaching; consists of methods and forms of knowledge assessment.

In the module-based teaching system, the rating evaluation system is used to evaluate students' knowledge, skills, and abilities. In it, all the student's educational activities, that is, the knowledge acquired and mastered in the classroom and outside the classroom, are evaluated by giving points. In turn, young personnel studying in higher education will become

competitive personnel who can work independently in their fields and think independently when necessary, along with becoming mature specialists in their fields.

It is necessary to activate the student's independent learning during the educational process. Independent education is characterized by the student's choice and implementation of the ways of posing, solving, self-control and evaluation. Currently, the educational process in higher education is aimed at the comprehensive formation of specialists, and in the conditions of their acquisition of certain professional knowledge, qualifications and skills, they must carry out comprehensive systematic work on the development and management of students' cognitive activities. In higher education, the teaching process should be subordinated to the acquisition of a large amount of information, the formation of effective, creative thinking, the development of the individual's intellectual potential, logical analysis and comprehensive processing of information. One of the important conditions for the organization of the educational process in the training of specialists in accordance with modern requirements is the activation of independent educational activities of students. In the system of independent education of students, the content of independent education is its basis. The content of independent education consists of independent education materials, the activities of the teacher and students. Communication between teacher and student plays a key role in this. The main tool for independent learning is independent learning materials.

Results:

One of the important requirements for the organization of modern education is to achieve high results in a short time without spending too much mental and physical effort. Forming specific skills and competencies based on the delivery of specific theoretical knowledge to students in a short period of time, monitoring their activities, evaluating the level of theoretical and practical knowledge acquired by them requires high pedagogical skills and a new approach to the educational process from the teacher. The introduction of new pedagogical technologies into the educational process is emphasized in the "National Personnel Training Program". Pedagogical technology is a systematic approach to the educational process, in which technical and human capabilities are taken into account in the organization of the educational process, and their interaction is the basis for creating optimal forms of education. Pedagogical technologies can be divided into the following components:

- social requirements imposed on the person of education and training participants;
- professional training of members of cooperative activities;
- the purpose, content, essence, means of implementation of the educational process;
- differentiation of the educational process;
- creativity.

That is, a person:

- 10% when he reads the source himself;
- 20% when he heard the information;
- 30% when he saw the event, event or process that happened;
- 50% when seeing the incident, event or process and hearing information about them;
- 80% when he/she transmits information (*speaks, demonstrates knowledge*);

Discussion:

- The following are distinguished as signs of independent work:
- the presence of a cognitive or practical task, a problematic issue;
- assignment time; manifestation of mental stress;
- conscientiousness, independence and activity of students in the process of solving assigned tasks;
- management of students' independent, knowledge and practical activities.

Thus, the main part of independent work is the knowledge or problematic task that determines the entire learning process. Independent work has the character of an activity, and therefore it can be divided into components that are characteristic of the activity: motivational communication, defining a specific task, choosing methods of implementation, managing communication, management. The following conditions must be met for successful independent work:

- motivation of the educational task;
- clear description of cognitive tasks;
- the algorithm, method of doing the work, the student's knowledge of the methods of doing it;
- that the teacher clearly defines the forms of the report, the scope of work, and the time of its submission;
- determining the types of consulting assistance (adjustment, thematic, problem consultations);
- criteria for evaluation, reporting, etc.;
- types and forms of supervision (seminar, tests, seminar, etc.).

Independent work includes repetition and creative processes in the student's work. Depending on this, three levels of independent work are distinguished.

Pedagogical technologies of organizing and managing independent education for students provide a differentiated approach, taking into account the level of intellectual development of students, as well as professional and general theoretical training, personal capabilities and inclinations.

The main characteristics of independent work of students:

- the presence of a cognitive or practical task, a problematic question or task and the time of their completion, solution;
- independent activity of students in the process of solving set tasks;
- to have independent activity skills;
- management and self-management of students' independent knowledge and practical activities.

The main point of independent work is cognitive or problematic. This is the presence of a task that determines the independent work process, prepares for the performance of educational and professional tasks, and ensures independent decision-making.

The main functions of independent work of students: cognitive, prognostic, corrective and educational.

Cognitive function is determined by the student's acquisition of systematized knowledge in subjects. Predictive function is the ability to anticipate and evaluate both the possible outcome and the performance of the task in time. Corrective function is the ability to adjust one's activity in time. Formation of independence as a function of education-characteristics.

The more independence the student is given, the more precisely the amount of knowledge he should learn in each subject should be determined. There is a subject for this - knowledge bases containing a list of basic concepts and rules, as well as the rationale for their acquisition (*reproductive, constructive or creative level*). The model of mastering the knowledge base on the subject should clearly define which of the listed concepts, theoretical and practical knowledge should be learned at the creative, and which, respectively, at the repetitive and constructive levels. Appropriate control forms should be provided in each thematic knowledge base.

Usually, a student cannot immediately assess his abilities and capabilities. Therefore, the process of self-organization of educational activities is divided into relatively separate periods:

- elementary organization that ensures the direct participation of the teacher in the students' activities to determine the causes of errors;
- self-organization that does not require the direct participation of the teacher in the process of independent formation of students' knowledge.

Conclusion:

Thus, a number of conditions are necessary for the effectiveness of students' independent work. First, provide a combination of volumetric class and independent rabots. Second, methodologically correct organization of student work in the auditorium and outside, including the use of new technologies for organizing students' independent knowledge, scientific and production activities. In addition, clearly defining the goals and tasks of independent work; conscious attitude of students to the need for independent work;

- existence of reasonable content for independent work;
- distribution of students by levels based on existing differences in self-sufficient learning and cognitive activity, their motivation and ability to organize self-sufficient work;
- the amount of independent practical work to be performed by each student in a certain academic period, concrete practical work and recommendations for their implementation;
- to know the requirements for the assessment of each work by the teacher;
- the opportunity to receive the necessary advice from the teacher in time.

Measures to ensure control over the organization and progress of independent education and encourage the student for its quality performance. This condition must be present in one or another form in the first three, so that control becomes not an administrative condition, but a complete didactic condition that affects the effectiveness of students' independent work in general

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 08.10.2019 No. PF-5847.
2. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated April 20, 2017 "On measures to further develop the higher education system".
3. Ishmukhamedov R.J. Ways to increase the effectiveness of education with the help of innovative technologies. T. 2004.

4. Muslimov N.A., Kuysinov O.A. Organization of independent education in the training of teachers of vocational education. Methodical guide. Tashkent: TDPU. 2006.
5. Orinov V. "ECTS credit-module system in higher education institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan: Basic concepts and rules." It was prepared in cooperation with El-Yurt Umid Foundation and the Council of Higher Education of the Republic. Manual. August 10, 2020.
6. Koysinov O.A. Development criteria for ensuring integrity in the continuing education system. Republic-wide scientific and technical conference on "Modernization of technology and professional education, problems and solutions". Bukhara. 20.11.2020.